

Title

A simple overview on chromosomes: structure , types , and special chromosomes, functions

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Abstract

A Chromosome is a molecule that decides sex of a character/ organism. The main function of Chromosomes is to carry genetic material from one generation to another and plays an important role in reproduction, growth, repair, important for survival.

Keywords

Chromosomes,Chromatin,Centromers,Special Chromosomes.

Introduction

Chromosomes are thread-like structures present in the nucleus ,wrapped in chromatids.

Centromers Contribution:-

Centromers attach the two sister chromatids.

- Contains spindle fibre,during cell division chromatids get attached with spindle fibre and later split at opposite poles.
- No. and shape of centromers varies in each chromosome.
- Centromer divides chromatids in long arm and short arm.
- Centromeres containing kentochores have specific DNA .
- Kentochores contain special protein.
- Known as primary constriction.

Structural organization and chemical composition of ~~centromere~~ centromeres :-

Chromatin:-

- Made up of DNA, RNA and Proteins.
- Plays role during cell cycle and Cell division during Interphase.
- During cell division chromatin gets condensed and chromosomes get visible.

Two types:-

- a. Heterochromatin.
- b. Euchromatin.
- Heterochromatin:- The dark stained side of DNA is called Heterochromatin.

- It contains tightly packed DNA which is genetically inactive.

chromatin

Heterochromatin

A epigenetic view

- Euchromatin:-
- Lightly stained side of DNA
- It contains loosely packed and active DNA.

Types of Chromosomes:-

- Monocentric.
- Holocentric.
- Acentric.
- Dicentric.
- Telocentric.
- Acrocentric.
- Submetacentric.
- Metacentric.

Special Chromosomes

- Giant Chromosomes:-
- Are very large compared to normal Chromosomes.
- Also called Megachromosomes.
- Has two types:-

Polytene Chromosomes:-

- Also known as salivary gland Chromosome.
- Discovered /Found in structure of nuclei in secretory glands.
- Discovered by Balbiani.
- Painter and Heitz later rediscovered them in the salivary glands of fruit flies and recognised them as special chromosomes.
- Also called polytene because of presence of chromonemata in them.

- Has a series of dark and clear bands called interband.

Polytene chromosome

- mRNA formation takes place due to the presence of balbiani rings.

Lampbrush Chromosome-

- First discovered in oocytes of salamanders.
- The name of the lampbrush chromosome was given because of its appearance, its shape was like a brush.
- Occur in oocytes in vertebrates and invertebrates.
- Also found in algae.
- 10,000 haploid sets of chromosomes are present.

lampbrush chromosome :-

chromosomes (-)

8 - chromatin loop

Chromatid

Chromatids

Telomers

- Part of chromosomes.
- Size decreases with age,
- Prevents fusion of chromosomes segments.

as it has wrapped structure contains chromosomes inside

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Structural and chemical organization of Telomeres :-

Telomeres are a part of chromosome.

Telomeres gets shorten with age.

Telomeres prevents the fusion of chromosome segments.

∴ Ageing process of Telomeres

Conclusion-

Chromosomes are essential structures that store genetic information and protect too.

